

Photoinduced reactions : Phototransformations of 2-aryl-3-(methoxymethoxy)-chromones

Ramesh C. Kamboj*, Mandeep Thakur, Surinder Berar, Urmila Berar, Zeba N. Siddiqui^a and Satish C. Gupta

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, Haryana, India

E-mail : rckamboj@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-1744-238277

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract : Photochemical cyclisation of 3-methoxymethyl ethers of 3-hydroxychromones to angular tetracyclic dihydro- and dehydrogenated compounds is studied. The product formation is explained on the basis of type-II hydrogen abstraction by the excited C=O group.

Keywords : 3-Alkoxyalkoxychromone, H-abstraction, 1,4-biradical.

Introduction

Chromones¹ are the most important naturally occurring compounds present in plant kingdom. These compounds are permanently exposed to Sun and are prone to phototransformations. Many chromones are known to undergo photocycloadditions², photooxygenations³ and photoisomerisations⁴ involving both π - π^* and n - π^* transitions. 2-Aryl-3-alkoxychromones represent a type-II system with carbonyl chromophore having suitably placed γ -hydrogen for abstraction. The nature of 3-alkoxy as well as 2-aryl group⁵ largely influences the photoproduct formation. The primary photochemical pathway for the product formation is generation of 1,4-biradical through abstraction of γ -hydrogen from 3-alkoxy moiety by the photo-excited C=O group⁶. The nature of 3-alkoxy group has been found to have an effect on stability and isomerisation⁷ of 1,4-biradical and thus plays a major role in product distribution. The incorporation of methoxy group on -OCH₂ at 3-position of chromone(s) could have a major effect on the formation/fate of biradical. In view of this, the present investigation describes the study of chromones having 3-alkoxyalkoxy group with a variety of 2-aryl (phenyl, substituted phenyls, 2-thienyl, 2-furyl) groups.

Results and discussion

The required 2-aryl-3-methoxymethoxychromones **2a-2f** were synthesized by alkylation of 2-aryl-3-hydroxychromones⁵ **1a-1f** with methoxymethylchloride⁸.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of benzopyran **2a-2f**

Irradiation of **2a** through pyrex filter in methanol using 365 nm light source under anaerobic conditions led to photoproducts **3a** (20%), **3a'** (22%) and **4a** (11%). Besides, some starting substrate (30%, co-tlc, m.m.p.) was recovered. The compound **2b** behaved as sister of **2a** upon similar irradiation (Scheme 2). The photolysis of **2c** under identical conditions also provided similar photoproducts **3c** and **4c** along with an additional photoproduct **5c**, a dehydrogenated tetracyclic compound.

Scheme 2. Photolysis of compound 2a-2c.

In contrast, irradiation of **2d-2f** in dry benzene, using pyrex filter, resulted exclusively in formation (Scheme 3) of cyclodehydrogenated products **5d-5f**.

Scheme 3. Photolysis of compound 2d-2f.

The formation of tetracyclic photoproducts **3a-3c**, **3a'** and **3b'** showed that H-abstraction by the photo-excited carbonyl to produce biradical **6** is the preferred pathway of the reaction. The initially formed biradical **6** could cleave to give **4a-4c** (Scheme 4). The reason for such cleavage could be the presence of $-OCH_3$ group on to the $-OCH_2$ group. It is known that any electron donating group always weakens the β,γ -bond and helps in its cleavage⁹.

Scheme 4. Mechanism of photoproduct formation.

The products **3a-3c**, **3a'** and **3b'** has been expected to be formed through the bond formation between $-CH-$ and the β -carbon of the 2-aryl ring followed by sigmatropic 1,5-H migration in enol **7**. The dehydrogenated products

5d-5f and **5e** are formed by the expulsion of H_2 during above mentioned cyclisation process⁶.

From the above account it is clear that when 2-aryl moiety is furyl, only photocyclisation (**3a**, **3b**) occurs whereas in case of phenyl only photodehydrogenated products **5d-5f** are formed. With thiophene both photocyclisation (**3c**) and photodehydrogenation (**5c**) have been observed. For such difference, the only assignable reason could be the difference in electron density on the ring moiety at C-2 which results in different degree of aromaticity in photoproducts being formed. The aromatic character increases from furan via thiophene to benzene. Consequently, the gain in energy by dehydrogenation is higher in the case of **5d-5f** and that may explain the exclusive formation of these products. The dehydrogenation re-establishes aromaticity. Since the aromatic character is less expressed in the case of thiophene, the dehydrogenation is less dominant in these cases (**5c**). Obviously, the low aromatic character of furan is insufficient to favour formation of dehydrogenation products.

The structures of all the photoproducts could be confirmed by comparison of their IR/¹H NMR/¹³C NMR spectra with those of starting substrates **2a-2f**. The IR spectra of compounds **4a-4c** exhibited a strong absorption at 1655–1659 cm^{-1} ($C=O$) and the ¹H NMR spectra showed characteristic peak $\delta \sim 6.75$ (1H, s) due to H-3. The tetracyclic photoproducts **3a-3c**, **3a'** and **3b'** in their ¹H NMR spectra showed absence of resonances corresponding to $-OCH_2-$ (s, δ 5.45) and H-3 when compared to their respective starting substrates **2a-2c**. In compound **3a**, the spectrum showed new resonances due to bridgehead protons H-11b and H-3a at δ 5.22 (d, $J_{11b,3a}$ 10.2

Hz) and 3.50 (d{dd}, $J_{3a,3}$ 2.7 Hz, $J_{3a,11b}$ 10.2 Hz, $J_{3a,4}$ 3.9 Hz) respectively which were confirmed by decoupling experiments. Decoupling of resonance at δ 3.50 (d{dd}, H-3a) converted the doublets at δ 5.22 (H-11b) and δ 5.00 (H-4) to singlet. The H-4 appeared at δ 5.00 (d, $J_{4,3a}$ 3.9 Hz). The photoproducts **5c-5f** showed IR absorption between 1630–1650 cm^{-1} owing to pyrone C=O group. In their ^1H NMR spectra, the proton H-5 (H-4 in **5c**) was found almost in the aromatic region of spectrum between δ 6.58–6.80.

The stereochemical features of the tetracyclic compounds **3a-3c**, **3a'** and **3b'** are evident by the correlation between the coupling constants (J) and the dihedral angle¹⁰ (Φ). The vicinal coupling constant (J) between H-11b and H-3a was found to be ~ 10.2 Hz that shows the *cis*-fusion of ring C and D with Φ value close to 0° . This is in conformity to our earlier observations⁵ as well as to naturally occurring pterocarpans^{11,12} which possess a close similarity with the photoproducts under consideration.

Regarding the inter-relationship between H-3a and H-4 in **3a-3c**, $J_{3a,4} \sim 4.0$ Hz amply makes them to be in *cis*-disposition with dihedral angle $\sim 60^\circ$. In such conformations the methoxy group at C-4 occupies Ψ -axial position on Ψ -chair conformation of ring C (Fig. 1). It may be mentioned here that in carbohydrate chemistry, an alkoxy group like $-\text{OCH}_3$ is preferred in axial disposition¹³, which is rationalized on the basis of anomeric effect. As analyzed by the coupling constant and dihedral angle (H-3a, 11b, 4), the compounds **3a'** and **3b'** are the diastereomers of **3a** and **3b**. In the former, the $-\text{OCH}_3$ is above the plane whereas in the latter it is below the plane of the molecule.

Fig. 1. 3D structure of compound **3a**.

Conclusion :

The photochemistry of 3-alkoxyalkochromones gives rise to tetracyclic photoproducts by cyclisation of 1,4-

biradical generated *in situ*. The extent of dehydrogenation during cyclisation depends upon the electron density on 2-aryl ring. The inclusion of methoxy group in 3-alkoxy moiety has been found to affect the product stereochemistry and dealkoxylation process.

Experimental

General :

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are thus uncorrected. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz Bruker spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were recorded on a Buck Scientific 500 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. Elemental analysis was carried on Perkin-Elmer 2400 instrument. TLC plates were coated with silica gel G (suspended in CHCl_3 -MeOH) and iodine vapours were used as visualizing agent. The columns for purification were packed with silica gel 100–200 mesh in petroleum ether (60–80 $^\circ\text{C}$)-benzene (9 : 1) and left overnight before use. The elution was carried out with increasing proportion of benzene in petroleum ether-benzene mixture. To maintain inert atmosphere during photolysis 99.9% dry N_2 gas was continuously bubbled through the reaction solution.

Synthesis of chromones **2a-2f** :

6-Chloro-2-(2'-furyl)-3-methoxymethoxy-7-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, **2a** :

To a suspension of 6-chloro-2-(2'-furyl)-3-hydroxy-7-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran **1a** (3.2 g, 0.01 mol), freshly ignited K_2CO_3 (1.0 g) and tetra-*n*-butylammonium iodide (200 mg) in dry acetone (30.0 ml) methoxymethylchloride (0.8 g, 0.01 mol) was added dropwise. The mixture was stirred under reflux for 2 h during which the colour of the reaction mixture changed from yellow to white. A subsequent filtration of the reaction mixture followed by distillation of the solvent yielded a gummy product that was crystallized from ethanol to afford the compound **2a**. Yield 67%, white solid; m.p. 114–115 $^\circ\text{C}$; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1635 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.18 (1H, s, H-5), 7.71 (1H, m, H-5'), 7.47 (1H, s, H-8), 7.44 (1H, d, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.6 Hz, H-3'), 6.64 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.6 Hz, $J_{4',5'}$ 1.8 Hz, H-4'), 5.45 (2H, s, $-\text{OCH}_2-$), 3.50 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 2.51 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 16.88 (C₇-CH₃), 57.31 ($-\text{OCH}_3$), 96.48 ($-\text{OCH}_2-$), 112.50 (C-3'), 117.17 (C-4'), 120.01 (C-8), 123.40 (C-10), 125.48 (C-6), 130.09 (C-2), 136.80

(C-3), 137.97 (C-5), 145.05 (C-7), 146.60 (C-5'), 148.51 (C-2'), 153.48 (C-9), 172.87 (C-4) (Found : C, 59.81; H, 4.05. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{13}ClO_5$: C, 59.92; H, 4.09%).

The other ethers **2b-2f** were synthesized by reacting 3-hydroxychromone **1b-1f** respectively with methoxymethyl chloride under the reaction conditions as used for compound **2a**.

2-(2'-Furyl)-3-methoxymethoxy-6-methyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, 2b :

Yield 67%, white solid; m.p. 104–105 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1638 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.02 (1H, d, $J_{m,o}$ 2.1 Hz, H-5), 7.71 (1H, m, H-5'), 7.50 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.1 Hz, 8.7 Hz, H-7), 7.42 (1H, d, J_o 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.16 (1H, d, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.3 Hz, H-3'), 6.65 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.3 Hz, $J_{4',5'}$ 1.8 Hz, H-4'), 5.45 (2H, s, $-OCH_2-$), 3.50 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 2.47 (3H, s, $-CH_3$); $\delta^{13}C$ 20.98 (C_6-CH_3), 58.31 ($-OCH_3$), 97.85 ($-OCH_2-$), 112.80 (C-3'), 117.16 (C-4'), 119.91 (C-8), 123.43 (C-10), 125.48 (C-2), 130.78 (C-3), 131.48 (C-5), 142.91 (C-6), 144.32 (C-7), 145.44 (C-5'), 148.00 (C-9), 153.18 (C-2'), 173.02 (C-4) (Found : C, 67.11; H, 4.90. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_5$: C, 67.13; H, 4.93%).

6-Chloro-3-methoxymethoxy-7-methyl-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, 2c :

Yield 65%, white solid; m.p. 130–132 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1638 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.18 (1H, s, H-5), 7.70 (1H, d, $J_{3',4'}$ 3.6 Hz, H-3'), 7.49 (1H, d, $J_{5',4'}$ 4.8 Hz, H-5'), 7.42 (1H, s, H-8), 7.32 (1H, dd, $J_{4',3'}$ 3.6 Hz, $J_{4',5'}$ 4.8 Hz, H-4'), 5.47 (2H, s, $-OCH_2-$), 3.53 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 2.52 (3H, s, $-CH_3$); $\delta^{13}C$ 18.88 (C_7-CH_3), 55.89 ($-OCH_3$), 97.50 ($-OCH_2-$), 114.31 (C-8), 117.97 (C-10), 127.09 (C-3'), 127.50 (C-4'), 129.77 (C-6), 130.78 (C-2), 131.08 (C-3), 131.97 (C-5'), 132.05 (C-5), 141.60 (C-2'), 148.51 (C-7), 156.53 (C-9), 173.48 (C-4) (Found : C, 56.98; H, 3.88. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{13}ClO_4S$: C, 57.06; H, 3.89%).

6-Chloro-3-methoxymethoxy-2-phenyl-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, 2d :

Yield 65%, white solid; m.p. 110–112 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1641 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.22 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-5), 8.05–8.02 (2H, m, H-2',6'), 7.62 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4 Hz, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.53 (4H, m, H-8,3',4',5'), 5.20 (2H, s, $-OCH_2-$), 3.09 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$); $\delta^{13}C$ 54.44 ($-OCH_3$), 97.51 ($-OCH_2-$), 119.76 (C-8), 125.10 (C-3), 125.19 (C-2',6'), 128.43 (C-10), 129.08 (C-4'), 130.72

(C-3',5'), 130.77 (C-6), 130.86 (C-2), 133.79 (C-5), 137.85 (C-1'), 143.73 (C-7), 157.14 (C-9), 173.14 (C-4) (Found : C, 64.31; H, 4.09. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{13}ClO_4$: C, 64.46; H, 4.14%).

6-Chloro-3-methoxymethoxy-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, 2e :

Yield 68%, white solid; m.p. 103–105 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1642 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.22 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-5), 8.06 (2H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.62 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4 Hz, 8.7 Hz, H-7), 7.48 (1H, d, J_o 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.05 (2H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.23 (2H, s, $-OCH_2-$), 3.91 (3H, s, $C_4'-OCH_3$), 3.20 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$); $\delta^{13}C$ 54.44 ($-OCH_3$), 57.45 ($C_4'-OCH_3$), 96.43 ($-OCH_2-$), 115.67 (C-3',5'), 118.76 (C-8), 124.45 (C-3), 125.19 (C-2',6'), 127.60 (C-1'), 128.43 (C-10), 130.77 (C-6), 131.26 (C-2), 132.19 (C-5), 142.89 (C-7), 156.14 (C-9), 161.34 (C-4'), 173.14 (C-4) (Found : C, 62.31; H, 4.33. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{15}ClO_5$: C, 62.35; H, 4.36%).

6-Chloro-3-methoxymethoxy-2-(3',4',5'-trimethoxyphenyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, 2f :

Yield 69%, white solid; m.p. 92–94 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm^{-1}) 1644 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.22 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-5), 7.62 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4 Hz, 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.53 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-8), 7.50 (2H, s, H-2',6'), 5.22 (2H, s, $-OCH_2-$), 3.94 (9H, s, $C_3'-OCH_3$, $C_4'-OCH_3$, $C_5'-OCH_3$), 3.21 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$); $\delta^{13}C$ 54.40 ($-OCH_3$), 57.86 ($C_3',4',5'-OCH_3$), 96.67 ($-OCH_2-$), 104.12 (C-2',6'), 119.76 (C-8), 124.78 (C-3), 129.08 (C-10), 129.76 (C-6), 129.92 (C-1'), 130.80 (C-2), 130.86 (C-5), 135.90 (C-4'), 142.09 (C-7), 154.78 (C-3',5'), 157.09 (C-9), 172.56 (C-4) (Found : C, 59.00; H, 4.65. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{19}ClO_7$: C, 59.05; H, 4.71%).

Photolysis of chromones 2a-2f :

General procedure : Solution of **2a** in dry methanol (0.0005 M) was placed in pyrex vessel and irradiated for 45 min with a 125 W medium pressure mercury lamp under N_2 atmosphere. The reaction was monitored by tlc as well as 1H NMR (Bruker, 300 MHz) of mixture at regular interval of 10 min. The photoproducts were separated by extensive column chromatography/preparative tlc and identified by comparison of their spectral data with that of starting substrate. The other substrates **2b-2c** were photolysed under the similar conditions of solvent while the substrates **2d-2f** were photolysed in dry benzene keeping the other parameters same.

Compound 3a : Yield 20%, white solid; m.p. 163–165 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1644 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.15 (1H, s, H-7), 7.33 (1H, s, H-10), 6.48 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-2), 5.22 (1H, d, *J*_{11b,3a} 10.2 Hz, H-11b), 5.06 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-3), 5.00 (1H, d, *J*_{4,3a} 3.9 Hz, H-4), 3.50 (1H, d{dd}, *J*_{3a,3} 2.7 Hz, *J*_{3a,11b} 10.2 Hz, *J*_{3a,4} 3.9 Hz, H-3a), 3.42 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 2.42 (3H, s, -CH₃); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 16.45 (C₉-CH₃), 49.32 (C-3a), 47.42 (C₄-OCH₃), 65.86 (C-11b), 100.65 (C-4), 100.87 (C-3), 119.34 (C-10), 123.48 (C-11a), 126.05 (C-6a), 128.32 (C-8), 130.12 (C-5a), 135.03 (C-7), 144.34 (C-2), 147.35 (C-9), 154.07 (C-10a), 173.04 (C-6) (Found : C, 59.83; H, 4.05. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃ClO₅ : C, 59.92; H, 4.09%).

Compound 3a' : Yield 22%, white solid; m.p. 196–197 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1644 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.22 (1H, s, H-7), 7.41 (1H, s, H-10), 6.48 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-2), 5.44 (1H, d, *J*_{11b,3a} 9.9 Hz, H-11b), 5.10 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-3), 5.00 (1H, d, *J*_{4,3a} 3.6 Hz, H-4), 3.60 (1H, m, H-3a), 3.42 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 2.42 (3H, s, -CH₃) (Found : C, 59.78; H, 4.07. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃ClO₅ : C, 59.92; H, 4.09%).

Compound 4a : Yield 11%, white solid; m.p. 170–171 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1659 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.18 (1H, s, H-5), 7.65 (1H, m, H-5'), 7.42 (1H, s, H-8), 7.14 (1H, d, *J*_{3',4'} 3.3 Hz, H-3'), 6.75 (1H, s, H-3), 6.63 (1H, dd, *J*_{4',3'} 3.3 Hz, *J*_{4',5'} 1.8 Hz, H-4'), 2.54 (3H, s, -CH₃); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 14.82 (C₇-CH₃), 105.27 (C-3), 112.60 (C-3'), 113.29 (C-4'), 119.75 (C-8), 123.28 (C-10), 125.48 (C-6), 131.89 (C-5), 143.00 (C-7), 145.97 (C-5'), 146.19 (C-2'), 154.03 (C-9), 155.22 (C-2), 176.56 (C-4) (Found : C, 64.30; H, 3.42. Calcd. for C₁₄H₉ClO₃ : C, 64.51; H, 3.48%).

Compound 3b : Yield 15%, white solid; m.p. 169–171 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1645 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.06 (1H, d, *J*_m 2.1 Hz, H-7), 7.48 (1H, dd, *J*_{m,0} 2.1 Hz, 8.7 Hz, H-9), 7.42 (1H, d, *J*₀ 8.7 Hz, H-10), 6.48 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-2), 5.24 (1H, d, *J*_{11b,3a} 9.9 Hz, H-11b), 5.10 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-3), 5.00 (1H, d, *J*_{4,3a} 3.9 Hz, H-4), 3.50 (1H, d{dd}, *J*_{3a,3} 2.7 Hz, *J*_{3a,11b} 9.9 Hz, *J*_{3a,4} 3.9 Hz, H-3a), 3.54 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 2.46 (3H, s, -CH₃); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 20.85 (C₈-CH₃), 44.98 (C-3a), 48.56 (C₄-OCH₃), 69.86 (C-11b), 100.61 (C-4), 100.77 (C-3), 117.97 (C-10), 123.48 (C-11a), 125.15 (C-6a), 128.32 (C-5a), 134.56 (C-8), 135.03 (C-7), 139.74 (C-9), 147.35 (C-2), 154.07

(C-10a), 172.84 (C-6) (Found : C, 67.05; H, 4.88. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄O₅ : C, 67.13; H, 4.93%).

Compound 3b' : Yield 17%, white solid; m.p. 192–193 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1645 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 7.98 (1H, d, *J*_m 2.1 Hz, H-7), 7.42 (1H, dd, *J*_{m,0} 2.1 Hz, 8.7 Hz, H-9), 7.34 (1H, d, *J*₀ 8.7 Hz, H-10), 6.49 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-2), 5.45 (1H, d, *J*_{11b,3a} 10.2 Hz, H-11b), 5.06 (1H, t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-3), 5.00 (1H, d, *J*_{4,3a} 3.6 Hz, H-4), 3.56 (1H, d{dd}, *J*_{3a,3} 2.7 Hz, *J*_{3a,11b} 10.2 Hz, *J*_{3a,4} 3.6 Hz, H-3a), 3.42 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 2.38 (3H, s, -CH₃) (Found : C, 67.01; H, 4.90. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄O₅ : C, 67.13; H, 4.93%).

Compound 4b : Yield 18%, white solid; m.p. 172–174 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1655 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.02 (1H, d, *J*_m 2.1 Hz, H-5), 7.65 (1H, m, H-5'), 7.52 (1H, dd, *J*_{m,0} 2.1 Hz, 8.7 Hz, H-7), 7.42 (1H, d, *J*₀ 8.7 Hz, H-8), 7.16 (1H, d, *J*_{3',4'} 3.3 Hz, H-3'), 6.81 (1H, s, H-3), 6.63 (1H, dd, *J*_{4',3'} 3.3 Hz, *J*_{4',5'} 1.8 Hz, H-4'), 2.48 (3H, s, -CH₃); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 23.56 (C₆-CH₃), 105.07 (C-3), 112.34 (C-3'), 113.50 (C-4'), 119.05 (C-8), 123.12 (C-10), 125.09 (C-5), 130.90 (C-6), 142.90 (C-7), 145.08 (C-5'), 146.09 (C-9), 153.80 (C-2'), 156.00 (C-2), 174.80 (C-4) (Found : C, 74.18; H, 4.46. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₀O₃ : C, 74.33; H, 4.46%).

Compound 3c : Yield 22%, white solid; m.p. 171–173 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1648 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.12 (1H, s, H-7), 7.20 (1H, s, H-10), 6.18 (1H, dd, *J*_{2,3} 6.0 Hz, H-2), 5.50 (1H, dd, *J*_{3,3a} 2.1 Hz, *J*_{3,2} 6.0 Hz, H-3), 5.23 (1H, d, *J*_{4,3a} 2.7 Hz, H-4), 4.65 (1H, d, *J*_{11b,3a} 9.0 Hz, H-11b), 3.67 (1H, d{dd}, *J*_{3a,3} 2.1 Hz, *J*_{3a,11b} 9.0 Hz, *J*_{3a,4} 2.7 Hz, H-3a), 3.43 (3H, s, -OCH₃), 2.41 (3H, s, -CH₃); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 19.07 (C₉-CH₃), 41.79 (C-11b), 51.11 (C-3a), 54.84 (C₄-OCH₃), 96.41 (C-4), 118.01 (C-10), 119.66 (C-11a), 121.04 (C-3), 123.77 (C-16a), 125.70 (C-8), 129.64 (C-5a), 132.81 (C-2), 134.97 (C-7), 148.27 (C-9), 151.89 (C-10a), 173.06 (C-6) (Found : C, 57.10; H, 3.88. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₃ClO₄S : C, 57.06; H, 3.89%).

Compound 4c : Yield 11%, white solid; m.p. 178–180 °C; $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 1649 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 8.17 (1H, s, H-5), 7.73 (1H, d, *J*_{3',4'} 3.6 Hz, H-3'), 7.60 (1H, d, *J*_{5',4'} 4.8 Hz, H-5'), 7.45 (1H, s, H-8), 7.20 (1H, dd, *J*_{4',3'} 3.6 Hz, *J*_{4',5'} 4.8 Hz, H-4'), 6.71 (1H, s, H-3), 2.53 (3H, s, -CH₃); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ 20.77 (C₇-CH₃), 105.76 (C-3), 119.75

(C-8), 122.87 (C-10), 125.29 (C-3'), 128.56 (C-4'), 128.61 (C-6), 130.53 (C-5'), 131.92 (C-5), 134.82 (C-2'), 143.01 (C-7), 154.06 (C-9), 159.09 (C-2), 176.58 (C-4) (Found : C, 60.66; H, 3.25. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_9ClO_2S$: C, 60.76; H, 3.28%).

Compound 5c : Yield 13%, white solid; m.p. 202–204 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1640 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.19 (1H, s, H-7), 7.56 (1H, d, $J_{2,3}$ 4.8 Hz, H-2), 7.38 (1H, s, H-10), 7.09 (1H, d, $J_{3,2}$ 4.8 Hz, H-3), 6.21 (1H, s, H-4), 3.57 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$), 2.44 (3H, s, $-CH_3$); $\delta^{13}C$ 19.07 (C₉-CH₃), 55.24 (C-OCH₃), 103.41 (C-4), 119.61 (C-10), 123.76 (C-11a), 125.24 (C-3), 127.97 (C-8), 128.10 (C-11b), 129.23 (C-3a), 131.21 (C-7), 133.23 (C-2), 133.45 (C-5a), 145.97 (C-6a), 148.27 (C-9), 154.19 (C-10a), 172.98 (C-6) (Found : C, 57.35; H, 3.30. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{11}ClO_4S$: C, 57.40; H, 3.31%).

Compound 5d : Yield 25%, white solid; m.p. 212–214 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1638 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.20 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-8), 8.00 (1H, m, H-1), 7.64 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4 Hz, 9.0 Hz, H-10), 7.60 (2H, m, H-2,3), 7.55 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-11), 7.45–7.42 (1H, m, H-4), 6.10 (1H, s, H-5), 3.64 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$); $\delta^{13}C$ 56.25 (C₄-OCH₃), 98.56 (C-5), 119.73 (C-11), 122.05 (C-4a), 123.50 (C-1), 125.26 (C-12a), 125.43 (C-2,4), 126.43 (C-3), 128.34 (C-9), 130.11 (C-12b), 130.73 (C-8), 131.28 (C-6a), 131.63 (C-7a), 143.30 (C-10), 158.01 (C-11a), 172.09 (C-7) (Found : C, 64.68; H, 3.48. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{11}ClO_4$: C, 64.88; H, 3.52%).

Compound 5e : Yield 29%, white solid; m.p. 217–218 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1640 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.20 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-8), 7.94 (1H, d, $J_{1,2}$ 8.7 Hz, H-1), 7.63 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4 Hz, 9.0 Hz, H-10), 7.55 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-11), 7.14 (1H, dd, $J_{2,1}$ 8.7 Hz, $J_{2,4}$ 2.1 Hz, H-2), 6.95 (1H, d, $J_{4,2}$ 2.1 Hz, H-4), 6.05 (1H, s, H-5), 3.93 (3H, s, C₃-OCH₃), 3.64 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$) (Found : C, 62.68; H, 3.81. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{13}ClO_5$: C, 62.71; H, 3.80%).

Compound 5f : Yield 26%, white solid; m.p. 212–214 °C; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 1638 (C=O); δ_H ($CDCl_3$) 8.20 (1H, d, J_m 2.4 Hz, H-8), 7.62 (1H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.4 Hz, 9.0 Hz, H-10), 7.57 (1H, d, J_o 9.0 Hz, H-11), 7.36 (1H, s, H-1), 6.27 (1H, s, H-5), 4.02 (3H, s, C₂-OCH₃), 3.98 (3H, s, C₃-OCH₃), 3.96 (3H, s, C₄-OCH₃), 3.64 (3H, s, $-OCH_3$); $\delta^{13}C$ 56.25 (C₄-OCH₃), 58.56 (C_{2,3,4}-OCH₃), 98.56 (C-

5), 105.23 (C-1), 112.23 (C-7a), 119.73 (C-11), 122.05 (C-4a), 123.50 (C-12a), 125.26 (C-6a), 128.43 (C-9), 130.73 (C-12b), 131.28 (C-8), 133.64 (C-3), 139.07 (C-10), 153.30 (C-2,4), 158.01 (C-11a), 172.09 (C-7) (Found : C, 57.25; H, 4.18. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{17}ClO_7$: C, 57.34; H, 4.23%).

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References

1. J. B. Harborne, "The Flavonoids : Advances in Research since 1986", Chapman and Hall/CRC Press, London, 1994.
2. J. W. Hannifin and G. O. Morton, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1966, 7, 5421; A. Nath and R. V. Venkateswaran, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1993, 281.
3. T. Matsuura, H. Matsushima and H. Sakamoto, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 6730; T. Matsuura, H. Matsushima and R. Nakashima, *Tetrahedron*, 1970, 26, 435.
4. N. Ishibe, S. Yutaka, J. Masui and Y. Ishida, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1975, 241; T. Matsuura, T. Takemoto and R. Nakashima, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, 6, 1539.
5. N. C. Yang and C. Rivas, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 2213; A. C. Waiss and J. Corse, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 2068; S. C. Gupta, A. Saini, D. Kumar, N. S. Yadav, K. Chand, S. Mor and S. N. Dhawan, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1995, 177; S. C. Gupta, S. Sharma, A. Saini and S. N. Dhawan, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1999, 2391; S. C. Gupta, N. S. Yadav and S. N. Dhawan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, 67, 770; S. C. Gupta, M. Yusuf, S. Sharma, A. Saini, S. Arora and R. C. Kamboj, *Tetrahedron*, 2004, 60, 8445; S. C. Gupta and S. K. Mukherjee, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1973, 14, 5073.
6. A. C. Waiss, R. E. Lundin, A. Lee and J. Corse, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 6213; T. Matsuura and H. Matsushima, *Tetrahedron*, 1968, 24, 6615; A. Feigenbaum, Y. Fort, J. P. Pete and D. Scholler, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1986, 51, 4424; J. Cossy and J. P. Pete, *Heterocycles*, 1984, 22, 97; A. B. Smith III and W. C. Agosta, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 95, 1961.
7. S. C. Gupta, M. Yusuf, S. Sharma, A. Saini, S. Arora and R. C. Kamboj, *Tetrahedron*, 2004, 60, 8445; S. C. Gupta, N. S. Yadav and S. N. Dhawan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, 30, 790.
8. A. J. Hill and D. W. T. Keach, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 257.
9. P. Mandal, A. Nath and R. V. Venkateswaran, *Tetrahedron*, 1996, 52, 7855.

Kamboj *et al.* : Photoinduced reactions : Phototransformations of 2-aryl-3-(methoxymethoxy) *etc.*

10. L. M. Jackman and S. Sternhell, "Applications of NMR Spectroscopy in Organic Chemistry", 2nd ed., Pergamon Press, New York, 1969, p. 281; C. A. G. Haasnoot, F. A. A. M. de Leeuw and C. Altona, *Tetrahedron*, 1980, **36**, 2783.
11. S. W. Banks, M. J. Steele, D. Ward and P. M. Dewick, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1982, 156.
12. K. G. R. Pachler and W. G. E. Underwood, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, **23**, 1817; S. H. Harper, A. D. Kemp and W. G. E. Underwood, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1965, 309; S. Shibata and Y. Nishikawa, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1963, **11**, 167; D. R. Perrin, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1964, **5**, 29.
13. R. U. Lemieux and S. Koto, *Tetrahedron*, 1974, **30**, 1933.